

Specific Case of an Internal Control-External Control (Bounded Domain)

YAMEOGO Pierre Claver
Dr. En Mathématiques(Ph.D)

Abstract:- We try to study the controllability of bounded domain Ω consisting of several heated materials. For this, we will use the functional $J(u)$, which optimizes the cost. The objective is to bring the excess heat inside the domain and also on the border of the domain and it's this excess heat that is a function called control.

I. INTRODUCTION

Let Ω be a bounded domain made up of heated materials, we give ourselves the conductivity $k(x)$ at the point $x \in \Omega$, the heat source f in $L^2(\Omega)$, the temperature T_D imposed on Γ_D by the system, the flux PN imposed on Γ_N . Let's consider the following problem:

$$(S) \begin{cases} -div(k(x)\nabla y(x)) = f \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \gamma y = t_D \text{ on } \Gamma_D, \\ ky \frac{\partial y}{\partial n} = PN \text{ on } \Gamma_N. \end{cases}$$

II. PROBLEM

Let y_D be a given temperature.

How to act on the system (S) so that y is close enough to y_D ?

III. IDEA

It is a question of bringing a surplus of heat u so that y is as close as possible to y_D . This excess heat is a function called control. To leave a good choice of u , we must optimize the cost, which reflects what we want to achieve and the means at our disposal. What amounts to considering the functional $J(u)$ defined by:

$$J(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} g(y - y_D) dx + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2;$$

Where g is a definite function of Ω a value in $\mathbb{R}$. $G(y - y_D)$ makes is possible to minimize the difference between y and y_D , ϵ being very small serves not only to prove the existence and uniqueness of the solution but also to minimize the cost.

IV. PROBLEM

Is there $\bar{u} \in U$ such that:

$$J(\bar{u}) = \min_{u \in U} J(u);$$

- u is in the set of admissible controls,
- $\bar{u}$ is the optimal control
- $y = y(\bar{u})$ is the optimal state

- The function J is the objective function

However, there are two types of controls:

- Internal control,
- Border control

NB: we advise you to look at the course material on control for detailed proof.

V. INTERNAL CONTROL

It is a question of bringing the excess heat inside the domain. Let us consider the following example of control:

Let f in $L^2(\Omega)$, y_D belonging to $L^2(\Omega)$ and u be a nonempty closed convex set of $L^2(\Omega)$. Let $u \in U, y(u)$ be the solution of the following equation.

$$(S) \begin{cases} -\Delta y(u) = f + u \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \gamma y(u) = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma. \end{cases} (1)$$

Let's pose

$$J(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} (y - y_D) dx + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2, (2)$$

$$= \|y - y_D\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2.$$

So we get the following problem:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Does } \bar{u} \text{ exist in } U \\ J(\bar{u}) = \min_{u \in U} J(u) \end{cases} (3)$$

VI. RESOLUTION

$$f \in L^2(\Omega), u \in L^2(\Omega) \Rightarrow f + u \in L^2(\Omega),$$

For any z in $L^2(\Omega)$, we know the problem below:

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta z = g \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \gamma z = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma. \end{cases} (4)$$

Has a unique solution in $H_0^1(\Omega)$, therefore $y(u)$ is the unique solution of problem (11).

We define the following operation:

$$A = L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow L^2(\Omega)$$

$$g \mapsto A(g) = z.$$

Where z is the solution of equation (4). A thus defined is linear and continuous.

We have

$$A(f + u) = y(u).$$

By replacing $y(u)$ by its value in (2), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} J(u) &= \frac{1}{2} \|y(u) - y_D\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2, \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \|A(f + u) - y_D\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2, \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left\| \frac{1}{2} \|A(u)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \epsilon \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \right\| \right\} + \langle A(f) - y_D, A(u) \rangle, \\ &J_1(u) + \langle A(f) - y_D, A(u) \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$$J_1(u) = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left\| \frac{1}{2} \|A(u)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \epsilon \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \right\| \right\},$$

And $\langle A(f) - y_D, A(u) \rangle$ is a constant.

Minimizing the functional J amounts to minimizing the functional J_1 . We put:

$$a: L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$(u, v) \rightarrow \langle A(u), A(v) \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} + \langle u, v \rangle$$

$$l: L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$(u, v) \rightarrow \langle A(u) - y_D, A(v) \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}.$$

- a is bilinear, continuous, coercive and symmetric,
- l is continuous linear,
- u a nonempty closed convex set of $L^2(\Omega)$,

By Stampacchia's theorem, there exists a unique $\bar{u}$ in u .

The solution $\bar{u}$ is characterized by:

$$\begin{cases} \bar{u} \in u \\ a(\bar{u}, v - \bar{u}) \geq l(v - \bar{u}) \quad \forall v \in u \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Having obtained the existence and uniqueness of the solution, we are interested in giving the characteristics of $\bar{u}$. To do this, we introduce the optimality system. By interpreting, the reaction

$$a(\bar{u}, v - \bar{u}) \geq l(v - \bar{u}) \quad \forall v \in u, \text{ we obtain:}$$

$$\langle \bar{y} - y_D, A(v - \bar{u}) \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} + \epsilon \langle \bar{u}, v - \bar{u} \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} \geq 0.$$

The Conjoint state $\bar{p} \in H_0^1(\Omega)$ is the solution of the following problem:

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta \bar{p} = \bar{y} - y_D \text{ in } \Omega \\ \gamma \bar{p} = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma, \end{cases}$$

We therefore have

$$\langle \bar{p} + \epsilon \bar{u}, v - \bar{u} \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} \geq 0.$$

We get the following optimality system:

$$\begin{cases} \bar{u} \in u, \bar{p} \in H_0^1(\Omega), y(\bar{u}) \in L^2(\Omega) \\ (S01) \begin{cases} -\Delta y(u) = f + u \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \gamma y(u) = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma. \end{cases} \\ (S02) \begin{cases} -\Delta \bar{p} = \bar{y} - y_D \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \gamma \bar{p} = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma, \end{cases} \\ (S03) \langle \bar{p} + \epsilon \bar{u}, v - \bar{u} \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} \geq 0. \end{cases}$$

VII. PARTICULAR CASE

$$\text{If } u = L^2(\Omega) \text{ then } \bar{u} = \frac{1}{\epsilon} \bar{p},$$

$$\text{If } u = L^2_+(\Omega) \text{ then } \bar{u} = \frac{1}{\epsilon} (\bar{p})^- \text{ -NB:}$$

In the case of shareholder internal Control, we have

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta y(u) = f + \psi u \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \gamma y(u) = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma. \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Where } u \in \mathbb{R}, \quad \psi \in L^\infty(\Omega)$$

VIII. BORDER CONTROL

This is to bring the excess heat to the Boundary of the domain. Consider

The following boundary control example:

Let f in $L^2(\Omega)$, y_D belong to $L^2(\Omega)$, g a function of $L^2(T)$ and nonempty closed convex of $L^2(T)$. Let $u \in u$, $y(u)$ be a solution of the following equation:

$$(S1) \begin{cases} -\Delta y(u) = f \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \gamma y(u) = g + u \text{ on } \Gamma. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

We pose:

$$J(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} (y(u) - y_D) dx + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(T)}, \quad (7)$$

$$= \|y(u) - y_D\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(T)}^2.$$

IX. RESOLUTION

► Simplification

By setting:

$$y(u) = y_1(u) + z,$$

Where $y_1(u)$ is the solution of the problem:

$$(S2) \begin{cases} -\Delta y(u) = 0 \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \gamma y(u) = g + u \text{ on } \Gamma. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

And z belongs to $H_0^1(\Omega)$ solution de :

$$(S1) \begin{cases} -\Delta z = f \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \gamma z = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

System S_1 becomes

$$(S1) \begin{cases} -\Delta y(u) = 0 \text{ in } \Omega, \\ \gamma y(u) = g + u \text{ on } \Gamma. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

We pose :

$$J(u) = \frac{1}{2} \|y(u) - y_{D1}\|^2 + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2.$$

Where

$$y_{D1} = y_d - z.$$

► **Transposition formula**

We associate to (S₂) the following transposition equation:

$$(S1) \begin{cases} -\Delta y(u) = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \gamma y(u) = g & \text{on } \Gamma. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Let *f* be a function of $L^2(\Omega)$ admitting a unique solution, we get from ()

$$\int_{\Omega} (\Delta y_1(u)) z \, dx = 0 \Rightarrow \int_{\Omega} f z \, dx = \int_{\Omega} g \frac{\partial z}{\partial n} \, d\sigma.$$

Considering the following problem:

$$(PV) \begin{cases} \text{find } y \text{ in } L^2(\Omega) \text{ such that} \\ \forall f \in L^2(\Omega), \int_{\Omega} f y \, dx = - \int_{\Omega} g \frac{\partial z}{\partial n} \, dx. \end{cases}$$

$$l : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$g \mapsto - \int_{\Gamma} g \frac{\partial z}{\partial n} \, d\sigma.$$

l is linear and continuous application on $L^2(\Omega)$, by riesz's theorem, there exists a unique $y \in L^2(\Omega)$ such that

$$\langle f, g \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} = l(f); \|y\|_{L^2(\Omega)} = \|l\| \quad (\mathcal{L}(L^2(\Omega), \mathbb{R})).$$

We define the operator

$$A : L^2(\Gamma) \rightarrow L^2(\Omega)$$

$$g \mapsto A(g) = y_1$$

Replacing

$$A(f + u) = y(u)$$

In $J(u)$, We have:

$$J = J_1;$$

With

$$J_1(u) = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \|A(u)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \epsilon \|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \right\} + \langle A, A - y_{D1} \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}$$

We pose

$$a : L^2(\Omega) \times L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$(u, v) \mapsto \langle A(u), A(v) \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} + \langle u, v \rangle_{L^2(\Gamma)}$$

$$l : L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$v \mapsto - \langle A(u) - y_{D1}, A(v) \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}.$$

X. CONCLUSION

In short, to solve the problem we must optimize the cost according to the goal we are looking for and taking into account the means at our disposal. But the case here requires a good mastery of the solutions of optimal control and some demonstrations to prove the existence, uniqueness and stability of solutions. Also, we give some extensions to our investigation.

REFERENCES

- [1.] S. Agmon ; A. Douglis, L. Nirenberg ; estimates near the boundary for solutions elliptic partial differential equations satisfying general boundary conditions. Comm. Pure Appl. Math, 12(1959);623 – 727. II. id. 17 (1964),35-92.
- [2.] H. Antorienz; Newton's method and boundary value problems. 5. of computer and system sciences, 2(1968); 177-202.
- [3.] Boundary value problems for non linear ordinary differential equation pacific journal mat; 17(1966); 191-197.
- [4.] Bailey et L. Champine et P. Woltman ; Non linear two point boundary value problems. Accad. Press, 1968.
- [5.] A. V. Balakrishman; on a new computing technique in optimal control and its application to minimal time flight profile optimization. Proc. Not. Accad. Sc January 1968.
- [6.] E. J. Beltrami methods of non linear analysis and optimization. Accad. Press 1969.
- [7.] F. E. Browder, non linear elliptic boundary value problems. Bull. Amer Math. Soc, 69(1963).
- [8.] A. Friedman, Free boundary problems for parabolic equations. Molting of solids; J. Maths, 9(1959); 499-518.
- [9.] J. L. Lions; some non linear evolution equations. Bull. Soc. Math. France, 93(1965), 43-96.
- [10.] J. L. Lions and E. Magenos, Idem, Vol. 3, Dunod, 1969.
- [11.] O. A. Olinik; on the existence, uniqueness, stability and approximation of solution of Prandtl's system for the non boundary layer. Rend. Acc. Naz....., 41(1966), 32-40.
- [12.] V.I. CHESALIN, A problem with nonlocal boundary conditions for certain abstract hyperbolic equations, Diff. Uravn., 15 (1979), No. 11, 2104-2106,
- [13.] V.I. CHESALIN, A problem with nonlocal boundary conditions for abstract hyperbolic equations, Vestn. Beloruss. Gos. Univ. Ser. 1 Fiz. Mat. Inform., (1998), No. 2, 57-60,